

Design of Synchronous SEPIC Converter with Voltage control Strategy

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Abstract— In this paper a voltage control loop for the synchronous SEPIC (Single Ended Primary Inductance Converter) is designed with the help of PID (Proportional Integral Derivative) controller. The proposed converter avoids the limitations of traditional buck-boost converter such as inverted load voltage, higher ripple current at input side, voltage stress across the power electronic switches results in unreliable performance under wide range of input or output parameters. The proposed converter allows both buck and boost operation and also provides lower ripple current and increased efficiency. A PID controller is used in the voltage control loop for synchronous SEPIC converters. The proposed system is simulated in MATLAB/Simulink software.

Key words—DC-DC converters, Sepic converter, Load voltage control, PID control.

I. INTRODUCTION

A circuit that converts a DC source between one voltage range to another is called an electronic circuit. An electric power converter is a DC to DC converter. There are several kinds of DC-DC converters, include buck converters, which can only lower voltage, boost converters, which can only raise voltage, and buck-boost, C^ok, and synchronous SEPIC converters, which can both increase and decrease voltage. Because buck-boost converters only need simply one inductance and a capacitor as well, they can be more affordable. The buck-boost frequently becomes inefficient as a result. C^uk converters use an additional capacitor to alleviate both of these issues. When a C^uk or buck-boost converter operates, a lot of electrical stress is placed on its parts, which can lead to device malfunction or overheating. Each of these problems are handled by synchronous SEPIC converters. One type of DC/DC converter that permits a larger electrical potential (voltage) at generated than other DC/DC converters is the SEPIC. Similarly, in contrast to buck-boost converters, which offer output voltage that is negatively controlled, SEPIC converters operate in a closed loop and offer a positive, controlled, consistent load output based on the supplied input voltage. Whenever a short circuit occurs, the barrier of isolation provided by the series connected coupling capacitor shields the converter. The SEPIC converter's yield is controlled by duty cycle. Traditional power converters, like buck, boost, and buck-boost converters, are not able to maintain high efficiency over a large operating range, particularly when step-up and step-down voltage transformation is required. A SEPIC can have these characteristics, and it can also deliver a positive, controlled

voltage output in response to a particular supply voltage. Compared with other types of converters, including boost converters, SEPIC converters possess a number of benefits. Among these benefits are:

- **Input Voltage Range:** Unlike boost converters, which cannot accept voltage sources that are greater or lower compared to the load voltage, SEPIC converters facilitate this. This adaptability may be useful in some situations.
- **Isolation:** In certain power supply systems, SEPIC converters can offer segregation from the source and load.
- **Efficiency:** While working with large range of supply voltages, SEPIC converters are occasionally more efficient than boost converters.
- **Output Ripple:** One advantage of SEPIC converters over boost converters is their potential for reduced output ripple, which qualifies them for tasks requiring precise load voltage specifications.
- **Stress Reduction:** Because SEPIC converters can control the load voltage regardless of the event of supply voltage fluctuations, they may reduce the strain on the supplied voltage source.

In this article, Synchronous SEPIC converter is designed and a control loop is designed with PID controller and also focused on the synchronization by replacing the diode by a power electronic switch (MOSFET) creating the synchronous SEPIC converter. Hence positive controlled load voltage is generated for the provided source voltage either lower or higher than the source. The proposed converter is analysed with operational modes and design parameters and simulated. The design of the proposed converter is tested and verified with the prototype model of the converter.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The block diagram for the proposed converter is provided below in Fig 1:

Fig 1 Proposed synchronous sepic converter with voltage control loop

The synchronised SEPIC converter is given the DC Input. The SEPIC converter functions in this way similarly to a non-inverting buck boost converter. The SEPIC converter may raise or lower a source voltage when it is regulated by a PID controller. The SEPIC converter's outcome is the source of input for the PID controller. As a result, the PID controller is used to effectively control the duty cycle. The synchronous SEPIC converter's MOSFET receives a pulse that it may use to adjust the voltage by varying the duty period. The synchronised SEPIC converter receives its output from the PID controller. As a result, the output from the SEPIC converter is sent through the R-load.

Fig 2 Proposed synchronous sepic converter

Let V be the conversion device's load voltage, V_{in} its source voltage, and $L1$ its related inductor at the source end. The load-corresponding connection is made to $L2$. The supply voltage and switch $S1$ are connected in parallel to one another. $S2$ and $C1$ are connected in sequence. Throughout the course of operation, the power electronic switch is able to be turned ON and OFF. The series connected coupling capacitor, $C1$, and the load side capacitor, $C2$, hold the voltage, accordingly. The resistor load, denoted as R , is linked in parallel with $C2$. There are two operating modes for this synchronised SEPIC in the continuous conduction mode: "S1 is ON, S2 is OFF" and "S1 is OFF, S2 is ON."

MODE 1: In this, the switch $S1$ operates and the current flows across the inductor $L1$ as the inductors $L1$ and $L2$ are charging and the series connected coupling capacitor $C1$ is discharging.

Fig 3 Mode 1 operational circuit for synchronous sepic converter
MODE 2: In this, the switch $S2$ operates and the inductors $L1$ and $L2$ discharges and the series connected coupling capacitor $C1$ gets charged.

Fig 4 Mode 2 operational circuit for synchronous sepic converter

III. CONTROL STRATEGY OF DC-DC CONVERTER

In this, the controlled gate pulses are provided for the dc-dc converter switches. The reference DC voltage (V_{dc}^*) is checked with the measured DC voltage (V_{dc}) and the error dc voltage (V_E) is obtained as

The error voltage is then provided to controller, from which the reference controlled voltage V_C is obtained as follows

$$V_C(k) = V_C(k-1) + K_p \{V_E(k) - V_E(k-1)\} + K_i V_E(k)$$

Where k denotes the sampling time period. The pulses generated for the dc-dc converter is of by comparing the control signal V_C with high frequency carrier signal M_c as

If $M_c < V_C$, pulse is ON

If $M_c \geq V_C$, pulse is OFF

Fig 5 Control strategy for synchronous sepic converter

Design Procedure for SEPIC Converter:

The pulse width relation with the input and load voltage of sepic converter is given below as

$$D = \frac{V_{OUT} + V_D}{V_{IN} + V_{OUT} + V_D}$$

The calculation of inductance is performed by the following relation:

$$L1 = L2 = L = \frac{V_{IN} (min)}{\Delta I_L \times f_{sw}} \times D_{max}$$

The calculation of ripple current of boost inductance is performed by the following relation:

$$\Delta I_L = 0.2 * \frac{V_o}{V_{in}} * I_o$$

The coupling capacitance value of sepic converter is provided by the following relation:

$$\Delta V_{Cs} = \frac{I_{OUT} \times D_{max}}{Cs \times f_{sw}}$$

The capacitance value at the load side is provided by the following relation:

$$C_{out} \geq \frac{I_{OUT} \times D}{V_{ripple} \times 0.5 \times f_{sw}}$$

The ripple output voltage is calculated with the following equation:

$$\Delta V_{oc} = 2\% \text{ of } V_o$$

IV. SIMULATION & HARDWARE RESULTS

The simulation parameters for the proposed inverter are provided below in Table I:

TABLE I
Simulation Parameters

Input Voltage	15V
Input power	35W
Switching Frequency	50 KHz
Load Resistance	100 ohm
Load Voltage	25V

The simulation circuit for the sepic converter with closed loop pulse generation is provided below:

Fig 6 Simulation circuit for synchronous sepic converter

In this, the dc voltage source of 15V provides supply to the load of 25V, 35W using sepic converter with switching frequency of 50KHz.

The pulses are generated based on the duty ratio generated by PI controller. The PI controller output along with high frequency carrier signal and resultant pwm pulses are provided below:

Fig 7 Controller output with pwm pulse waveforms for synchronous sepic converter

Due to the pulses shown above, the inductor will be charging (pulse is ON) and discharging (pulse is OFF) and hence we get the required load voltage. The inductor currents along with pulses and load parameters are provided below:

Fig 8 Inductor current with load parameter waveforms for synchronous sepic converter

In this the load voltage is around 28V and load current is around 1.55A. The load voltage in comparison with source voltage is provided below:

Fig 9 Load and source voltage waveforms for synchronous sepic converter

In this the source voltage is around 15V and load voltage is around 27V and the voltage conversion ratio is around 1.8 times.

A hardware prototype model of proposed converter with input voltages of 12V is developed with 36V as output voltage with load resistance of 10 Kilo ohm. The hardware parameters is provided below in the following Table II.

TABLE II
Hardware Parameters

IRF 250N - MOSFET	200v, 30A
Capacitor	1000 μ F, 25V
TRANSFORMER	12V, 1A
TLP 250 - DRIVER IC	12V, 1.5A
CD 4050 BUFFER IC	3-18V, 0.32mA
12V REGULATOR 7812	12V, 1A
IN 4007 DIODE	700V, 1A
ARDUINO UNO CONTROLLER	7-12V, 20mA

The hardware circuit of sepic converter with 12V input and 30V output is provided below:

Fig 10 Hardware prototype model for synchronous sepic converter

Arduino uno control is used for generating the pulses for the proposed inverter and it is provided to driver circuit (TLP 250) in order to drive the mosfets IRF 250. The load voltage is provided below:

Fig 11 Load voltage of Hardware prototype model for synchronous sepic converter

The load voltage is around 32V.

CONCLUSION

In this closed loop synchronous SEPIC converter is designed with PID controller based voltage control loop. The proposed converter maintains the constant output voltage due to the feedback control circuitry. The converter parameters are measured along with the controller outputs in the simulation work. A hardware prototype model is designed with 12V input and 30V output and the working of the proposed system is validated and verified.

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